

CURRICULAR COMPETENCE THROUGH LEARNERS CAFETERIA

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Quality is never an accident; it is always a result of high intention, sincere efforts, intelligent direction, and skillful execution; it represents the wise choice of many alternatives.

Willa A. Foster: Quality in Education

Abstract

Curricular flexibility and learners' mobility is an issue that deserves an immediate attention. In order to confer with some degree of flexibility to learners, we ought to delineate course span in terms of credit hours with a minimum as well as a maximum permissible extent of time for a learner to complete the program of study. These requirements can be addressed by introducing credit based courses and credit accumulation.

Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) is an instructional package developed to ensemble the needs of students as per the contemporary changes in higher education. CBCS essentially implies: i) a restructuring of curriculum into small measurable units, defining the number of hours, and not weeks or months, to complete a given set of course; and ii) the evolution of a mechanism whereby these modules can be pooled in varied juxtaposition to allow a scholar to qualify any Certificate, Diploma or Degree.

CBCS represents a much-required shift in approach from teacher-centric to learner-centric education because here, the workload is estimated on the basis of time invested in learning, not in teaching. CBCS helps to record the course work and learners' workload rationally since all their activities are taken into account - not only the time, learners spend in lectures or seminars, but also the time they need for individual learning and preparation of examinations.

The Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) imminently fits into the emerging socio-economic milieu and may well respond to the academic and professional aspirations of the coming generations. In this wake, University Grants Commission has appealed to all institutions of higher education in India to mull over the strategies for implementation of CBCS and adoption of CFSD. Making the best use of modern communication and information technology, Indian institutions and higher education system can scale newer heights.

Keywords: Choice-Based Credit System, CATS, CBCS, CSFD, Cafeteria Model, ECTS, MHRD, UGC.

What is Choice Based Credit System?

Most of the Indian Universities and Colleges have been following marks or percentage based evaluation system, which is acting as a barrier for students' mobility from one institution to another. The University Grant Commission (UGC), after thorough deliberation with the educationists and experts, has made it obligatory to all HEIs to implement choice based credit system in their undergraduate (UG) and postgraduate (PG) courses.

CBCS is a model, wherein the students have a choice to choose from the prescribed courses, which are referred as core, elective or minor or soft skill courses and they can learn at their own pace and the entire assessment is grade-based on a credit system. The basic idea is to look into the needs of the students so as to keep up-to-date with development of higher education in India and abroad. CBCS aims to redefine the curriculum keeping pace with the liberalization and globalization in education. CBCS allows students an easy mode of mobility to various educational institutions spread across the world along with the facility of transfer of credits earned by students.

Salient Features of CBCS

- There is a uniform system for all central, state and other recognized universities.
- There are three main courses - Core, Elective and Foundation.
- There are also non-credit courses (not counted towards the computation of SGPA/CGPA) available which may be assessed as 'Satisfactory' or 'Unsatisfactory'.
- All the three main courses will be evaluated and accessed to provide for an effective and balanced result.

Broad Outline of CBCS

1. Core Course: A course, which should compulsorily be studied by a candidate as a core requirement.
2. Elective Course: A course which can be chosen from a pool of courses and which may be very specific, specialized, advanced or supportive to the discipline / subject of study or which provides an exposure to some other discipline / subject / domain to substantiate the proficiency / skills of the student.

Elective course can be discipline specific (DSE - which may be offered by the main discipline / subject) or generic (GE - it can belong to an unrelated discipline / subject, for sake of exposure) or a Dissertation or Project (an elective course designed to acquire special / advanced knowledge through a supplement study or project work, under the supervision of a faculty).

3. Ability Enhancement Courses (AEC): It could be either Ability Enhancement Compulsory Courses (AECC - courses based upon the content that leads to Knowledge enhancement, e.g, Environmental Science, English / MIL Communication) or Skill Enhancement Courses (SEC – value or skill based courses that are aimed at providing hands-on-training, skills, etc).

How does CBCS work?

CBCS has the following basic elements:

- Semesters: The assessment is done semester wise. A student progresses on the basis of the courses taken rather than time like three years for science, arts, commerce or four years for engineering etc. Each semester will have 15–18 weeks of academic work which is equal to 90 teaching days. There is flexibility in creating the curriculum and

assigning credits based on the course content and hours of teaching.

- Credit system: Each course is assigned a certain credit. When the student passes that course, he earns the credits which are based on that course. If a student passes a single course in a semester, he does not have to repeat that course later. The students can earn credits according to his pace.
- Credit transfer: If for some reasons, he cannot cope with the study load or if he falls sick, he has the freedom to study fewer courses and earn fewer credits and he can compensate this in the next semester.
- Comprehensive continuous assessment: There is a continuous evaluation of the student not only by the teachers but also by the student himself.
- Grading: UGC has introduced a 10-point grading system as follows:

O	Outstanding	10
A+	Excellent	09
A	Very Good	08
B+	Good	07
B	Above Average	06
C	Average	05
P	Pass	04
F	Fail	00
Ab	Absent	00

- A student obtaining Grade F shall be considered failed and will be required to reappear in the examination.
- For non-credit courses 'Satisfactory' or 'Unsatisfactory' shall be indicated instead of the letter grade and this will not be counted for the computation of SGPA / CGPA.
- The Universities can decide on the grade or percentage of marks required to pass in a course and also the CGPA required to qualify for a degree taking into consideration the recommendations of the statutory professional councils such as AICTE, MCI, BCI, NCTE etc.,
- The statutory requirement for eligibility to enter as assistant professor in colleges and universities in the disciplines of arts, science, commerce etc., is a minimum average mark of 50% and 55% in relevant postgraduate degree respectively for reserved and general category. Hence, it is recommended that the cut-off marks for grade B shall not be less than 50% and for grade B+, it should not be less than 55% under the absolute grading system. Similarly cut-off marks shall be fixed for grade B and B+ based on the recommendation of the statutory bodies (AICTE, NCTE etc.) of the relevant disciplines.

How is the credit counted?

One credit per semester is equal to one hour of teaching, which includes both lecture (L) or tutorial (T) or two hours of practical work / field work (P) per week. A study course can have

one, two or three components out of L, T and P. The total credits earned by a student for each semester is L+T+P.

On Par with the Global Grading System

All the major higher education institutions across the world are implementing a system of credits. For instance, we have the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) in Europe's universities, the National Qualifications Framework (NQF) in Australia. There is the Pan-Canadian Protocol on the Transferability of University Credits. In the UK, they have the Credit Accumulation and Transfer System (CATS). Even the systems operating in the US, Japan, etc. are based on credit system. In India, IITs, BITS-Pilani and NITs are implementing this system for years.

Implementation

- The CBCS may be implemented in Central / State Universities subject to the condition that all the stakeholders agree to common minimum syllabi of the core papers and follow common minimum curriculum as fixed by the UGC, up to a maximum permissible deviation of 20 %.
- UGC may prepare a list of elective papers, and the universities may go for further additions, as per the facilities available.
- Number of core papers for all Universities must be same for both UG Honors as well as UG Program.
- Credit score earned by a student for any elective paper has to be included in the student's overall score tally irrespective of whether the paper is offered by the parent university (degree awarding university / institute) or not.
- For the introduction of AE Courses, there can be two categories:
 - a) AE Compulsory Courses: The universities participating in CBCS system may have common curriculum for these papers. There may be one paper each in the 1st two semester viz. (i) English / MIL Communication, (ii) Environmental Science.
 - b) Skill Enhancement Courses: The universities may decide the papers they may want to offer from a common pool of papers decided by UGC or the universities may choose such papers themselves in addition to the list suggested by UGC. The universities may offer one paper per semester for these courses.
- The university / Institute may plan the number of seats per elective paper as per the facility and infrastructure available.
- Honours, in a discipline, may be awarded if a student completes 14 core papers in that discipline, with a minimum of 02 AECC, 02 SEC and 04 papers each from DSE and GE respectively.
- An undergraduate Program degree in Science disciplines may be awarded if a student completes 04 core papers each in three disciplines of choice, 02 AECC, 04 SEC and 2 papers each from DSE disciplines selected above, respectively.

- An Undergraduate program degree in Humanities / Social Sciences / Commerce may be awarded if a student completes 04 core papers each in two disciplines of choice, 02 core papers each in English and MIL respectively, 02 AECC, 04 SEC, 02 papers each from DSE disciplines selected above, respectively, and two papers from GE.
- The credit(s) for each theory paper /practical /tutorial /project / dissertation will be as per the details for B.Sc. Honours, B.A. / B.Com. Honours, B.Sc. program and B.A. / B.Com. programs above, respectively.
- Wherever a University requires that an applicant for a particular M.A. / M.Sc. / Technical / Professional course should have studied a specific discipline at the undergraduate level, it is suggested that obtaining 24 credits in the concerned discipline at the undergraduate level may be deemed sufficient to satisfy such a requirement for admission to the M.A. / M.Sc. / Technical / Professional course.
- The Universities / Institutes may offer any number of choices of papers from different disciplines under GE and DSE as per the availability of the courses / faculty.
- A student can opt for more number of Electives and AEC than proposed under the model curriculum of UGC. However, the total credit score earned will not exceed 160 credits for UG Honours and 140 credits for UG Program degree.
- The new scheme of UG courses should be given due consideration while framing the admission eligibility requirement for PG / Technical courses in Indian Universities / Institutions to ensure that students following inter and multi-disciplinary format under CBCS are not at a disadvantage. It is suggested that wherever required, obtaining 24 credits in particular discipline may be considered as the minimum eligibility, for admission in the concerned discipline, for entry to PG / Technical courses in Indian Universities/Institutions.

Merits of CBCS

- The CBCS offers a 'cafeteria' approach in which the students can choose courses of their own choice. It can be seen as a paradigm shift from the teacher-centric to learner-centric pedagogy.
- The credit system allows a student to study what he prefers in his own sequence as per his interests.
- Student may undertake as many credits as they can cope with (without repeating all courses in a given semester, if they fail in one / more courses). They can also opt for additional courses and can achieve more than the required credits.
- CBCS allows students to choose inter-disciplinary, intra-disciplinary courses, skill oriented papers (even from other disciplines as per their learning needs, interests and aptitude) and more flexibility for students).
- Inter college / university migration within the country and outside becomes easy with the transfer of Credits. This means that it will be easier for foreign universities to come and offer courses in India.

- CBCS makes education broad-based and at par with global standards. One can take credits by combining unique combinations, for example, Genetics with Economics, Microbiology with Environment Science etc.
- CBCS offers flexibility for students to study at different times and at different institutions to complete one course (ease mobility of students). Credits earned at one institution can be transferred.
- The students have more prospects for undertaking projects, assignments, vocational training and internships.
- The system will enable potential employers to assess the performance of students on a scientific scale.

Demerits of CBCS

- It would be difficult to calculate the exact marks.
- Work load of faculty would be increased, which may affect regular teaching.
- Maintaining compatibility among core papers and electives would be challenging, particularly for rural colleges with inadequate faculty.
- Offering programs of different nature may perplex weak learners.
- Mobility of students from one institution to another may aggravate problems.

Conclusion

In India, Higher Education is a complex system because it houses a surprising variety of courses and streams. Therefore, maintaining harmony, among all the streams / courses, is a tedious exercise. So far, different strategies have been adopted by different universities to achieve academic quality in all aspects, right from teaching-learning to examination, evaluation and grading system. Though it is assumed that implementation of CBCS would bring in a uniform evaluation system, yet the existing disparity between Central Universities, State Universities and Colleges in terms of infrastructure, teachers' efficiency, academic environment and institutional credibility cannot be overlooked.

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